

ANEX 1: Survey

1. **Sex:** Male () Female ()
2. **Age:** _____
3. **University:** _____
4. **Type of University:** Public () Private ()
5. **Current Career:** _____
6. **Year of Course of Study:** First () Second () Third () Fourth ()
Fifth () Sixth ()
7. **Country of Residence:** _____

8. About mistreatment in general, whether by students, teachers, or others.

Mark with (X) the situation you have experienced in the last year.

- | | |
|---|---------------|
| 0 | Never |
| 1 | Few times |
| 2 | Sometimes |
| 3 | Several Times |
| 4 | Always |
-

Psychological Abuse

- | | | | | |
|---|-------|-------|-------|-------|
| 1. They yelled at me. | () 1 | () 2 | () 3 | () 4 |
| 2. I have received negative or derogatory comments. | () 1 | () 2 | () 3 | () 4 |
| 3. I was humiliated. | () 1 | () 2 | () 3 | () 4 |
| 4. I was insulted. | () 1 | () 2 | () 3 | () 4 |
| 5. I have received unwarranted criticism. | () 1 | () 2 | () 3 | () 4 |
| 6. My gender has been mocked. | () 1 | () 2 | () 3 | () 4 |
| 7. My ethnicity (race or skin color) has been mocked. | () 1 | () 2 | () 3 | () 4 |
| 8. I received verbal threats. | () 1 | () 2 | () 3 | () 4 |

Physical Abuse

- | | | | | |
|--|-------|-------|-------|-------|
| 1. I have been beaten. | () 1 | () 2 | () 3 | () 4 |
| 2. I have been exposed to unnecessary risks. | () 1 | () 2 | () 3 | () 4 |
| 3. I have been assigned excessive work. | () 1 | () 2 | () 3 | () 4 |

Academic Abuse

1. I have been assigned tasks as punishment. 1 2 3 4
2. I have been threatened with failing a course. 1 2 3 4
3. I have experienced unfair competition from my peers. 1 2 3 4
4. Others have taken credit for my work. 1 2 3 4

Sexual Abuse

1. My gender was discriminated. 1 2 3 4
2. I have had sexual verbal advances or obscene comments made to me. 1 2 3 4
3. I have been discriminated against because of my sexual orientation. 1 2 3 4
4. I have been approached with indecent proposals. 1 2 3 4
5. I have been shown offensive images of a sexual nature. 1 2 3 4
6. I have been shown offensive body language of a sexual nature (obscene gestures, looks, touching, unnecessary approaches). 1 2 3 4
7. I have been touched without my consent. 1 2 3 4
8. I was sexually blackmailed. 1 2 3 4

9. In general, what is your satisfaction with:

Mark with (X).

- 0 Very Satisfied
- 1 Satisfied
- 2 Regular
- 3 Unsatisfied
- 4 Very unsatisfied
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1. The overall logistics of your university. 1 2 3 4
2. Teacher education. 1 2 3 4
3. University agreements. 1 2 3 4
4. The research conducted. 1 2 3 4